

The Concept of Global Maritime Axis Policy in Indonesian State Defense

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ABSTRACT:Indonesia is an archipelagic country with a dominating sea area, which is 2/3 of its area. Surrounded by a vast ocean, the government of Joko Widodo has made the Global Maritime Axis one of the guidelines for national development. This is done to revive the maritime spirit among the people. This research was conducted to determine the concept of the Global Maritime Axis policy in the defense of the Indonesian state. By using a qualitative descriptive method, the data to be taken comes from books, previous research, scientific articles, literature and news from official websites. Along with global developments, the forms of threats that exist are not only physical threats but also non-physical threats. With the existing sea area and sea lanes that are not only used for national but also international shipping lanes, it is necessary for the government to establish regulations related to law at sea considering the threats that enter through sea routes such as the threat of drugs, illegal activities to terrorism. The sinking of foreign ships that enter the Indonesian Territory illegally is one of the government's efforts to protect the territorial sea. In order to support the government's policy as the global's maritime axis, the government establishes strategies such as the construction of the sea highway and reaffirms that Indonesia is a maritime country.

KEYWORDS -Global maritime axis, Maritime security, Potential threats in maritime, Strategy, Territorial sovereignty

I. INTRODUCTION

In the 2014 Indonesian presidential election, Joko Widodo conveyed his ideas related to maritime-based economic development in order to create prosperity for the people of Indonesia which is often referred to as the Global Maritime Axis. Then when he was elected president of Indonesia, the idea he had created was used as a guide in the implementation of national development. In applying the ideas that he created, the government of President Joko Widodo and his staff made these guidelines in implementing national development, through a new agenda that was set to restore the maritime spirit by making Indonesia the global's maritime axis.

Indonesia is an archipelagic country located between two oceans, namely the Pacific Ocean and the Indian Ocean and is located between two continents, namely the Asian continent and the Australian continent. As the largest archipelagic country in the world, with 17,499 islands and a total area of around 7.81 million km², of course, Indonesia has abundant natural resources. Indonesia's ocean area of the total area is 3.25 million km² and 2.55 million km² is an EEZ (Exclusive Economic Zone). Of course, looking at the vast sea area of Indonesia, it can be said that Indonesia is a maritime country.

The importance of the role of the maritime sector for Indonesia has been known for a long time, in realizing this there is of course the need for integrity in maritime development in various aspects, such as politics, socio-culture, defense, infrastructure, and especially the economy. To support the concept of the Global Maritime Axis which has been stated in Presidential Regulation Number 2 of 2015 concerning the 2015-2019 National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN). In addition, to support the seriousness of this matter, Jokowi has capitalized on the national maritime potential, supported by the formation of the Maritime Security Agency through Presidential Instruction No. 178 of 2014 and the formation of the Coordinating Ministry for Maritime Affairs and Resources of the Republic of Indonesia according to Presidential Instruction No. 10 of 2015.

The concept of the global maritime axis in sector development Indonesia's maritime focus has been stated in five main pillars, namely:

1. Rebuilding Indonesian maritime culture as Indonesia's national identity that we are a maritime country.
2. Commitment in managing and conserving the nation's maritime resources with a focus on developing seafood through developing the fishing industry and placing fishermen as the main pillar
3. Commitment in prioritizing maritime infrastructure development, construction of transportation facilities and infrastructure and marine tourism.
4. Maritime diplomacy by optimizing soft power in dealing with regional threats and increasing bilateral and multilateral cooperation in the maritime sector
5. Building maritime security by preparing hard power to strengthen defense forces

Indeed, the beginning of Indonesia's struggle as a maritime country began with the Djuanda Declaration on December 13 1957 until the stipulation of Indonesia as an archipelagic state with UNCLOS 1982 which was ratified in Law No. 17 of 1985. In UNCLOS it must also be understood that Indonesia has major consequences for the defense system that must be built. When viewed from the geostrategy, where the Indonesian state is flanked between two oceans and two continents, thus making the Indonesian sea lanes a very important route and traversed by thousands of ships both in terms of national shipping and international shipping. The conflict that is often faced by Indonesia is that our country is located on the border with other countries, because in the border areas many of our natural resources are not managed properly.

Even though Indonesia is an archipelagic country where 2/3 of its area is water, it is unfortunate that maritime awareness among Indonesian people is still very lacking. So the concept of the Global Maritime Axis (PMD) is used as one of the key factors to secure Indonesia's maritime sovereignty and prosperity. Because with the many threats to marine safety, of course, it requires special attention and good national governance in order to realize a marine defense system that is able to maintain the sovereignty of the unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia.

II. METHOD

In this research using descriptive analytical. The aim is to produce research reports that provide comprehensive and analytical explanations. The discussion and research results are in the form of a study or critical analysis. Then for the approach used in this study is a qualitative approach. In addition, the data collection method is from books, previous research, scientific articles, literature and news from official websites.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Indonesia as the Global Maritime Axis

The concept of a maritime state is a country that can use and protect its marine territory. Through the Global Maritime Axis, Indonesia will restore Indonesia's identity as a large, strong, and prosperous maritime country through restoring Indonesia's identity as a maritime nation, securing maritime interests and security, empowering all maritime potentials for the sake of the nation's prosperity, economic equity through maritime highways and carrying out maritime diplomacy. in Indonesian foreign policy.

In fact, the government is working hard to build a strategic maritime power. Efforts to make Indonesia a maritime axis in the global is one of the government's main visions. The government's main plans to make Indonesia the global's maritime axis are: Development of maritime processes in terms of infrastructure, politics, socio-culture, law, security, and economy. Maintaining the sovereignty of the maritime territory of the Republic of Indonesia through the revitalization of marine economic sectors as well as developing and strengthening maritime connectivity. Rehabilitation of environmental damage and biodiversity conservation. Improving the quality and quantity of marine human resources.

The policies carried out by the government in realizing Indonesia as the global's maritime axis certainly need to be supported by a capable maritime defense force and become one of the national priorities. Because if it is not capable, it will be difficult for our country to realize Indonesia as the global's maritime axis. The ideals and agenda of the Joko Widodo administration will be the focus of Indonesia in the 21st century. Indonesia will become the Global Maritime Axis, a power that crosses two oceans as a prosperous and authoritative maritime nation. In guarding the vision of the Sea of the Nation's Future and supporting the Nawacita mission mandated by President Joko Widodo. Nawacita itself is the nine priorities in the development period of the next five years. Therefore, it is necessary to have a strong maritime defense strategy to build and develop and support the improvement of maritime culture in order to realize Indonesia as the global's maritime axis in order to achieve national goals.

Figure 1. Indonesian Archipelagic Sea Channel

Indonesia with a very wide geography of course prioritizes defense and security in the maritime area. In terms of military defense, the Navy as one of the main components operates with two basic strategies, namely maritime control and force projection. Then to support the government in the maritime sector in the maritime sector grand strategy order or commonly called the global maritime axis, the concept of this strategy is divided into two, namely:

1. Maritime strategy (military)
 - a) Means. To achieve the goal, it can be done through Force structure, Modernization, Readiness, and Sustainability.
 - b) Ways. To achieve the goal can be done through Mobility, and Ready on Arrival. Observing the facts of the development of submarine technology and the balance of power in the Asia Pacific region.
 - c) Ends. To achieve the goal can be through Command, Sea Control, Deterrence, Sea Denial, Fleet in Being and Power Projection. Indonesia's vast and strategic sea area for international waters, shipping lanes that are passed by various types of ships from various countries for their interests, can lead to conflict
2. National maritime strategy, namely through the formation of cooperation (Global/Regional Reach); Power Projection Ashore; Controlling the sea and sea lines of communication (Sea Control/Sea Line On Communication Protection); Broad sea security: Environmental, Economic, Political, Societal/Culture, Military/Defence.

3.2 Potential Threats in Maritime Axis Policy

The Indonesian government still has to be ready to face several challenges in an effort to realize its vision as the global's maritime axis. One of the challenges that must be faced by Indonesia is geography, where Indonesia has archipelagic provinces that are surrounded by sea so that it requires a connecting area. Indonesia has eight Indonesian provinces bordering the sea, namely Riau Islands, Bangka Belitung, NTT, NTB, North Sulawesi, Southeast Sulawesi, North Maluku, Maluku. The importance of maritime sector development is very important to be carried out in these eight provinces. As a country that has several islands directly adjacent to

other countries, Indonesia must also be able to manage maritime borders with neighboring countries in order to maintain mutual security.

The potential threats that may occur in Indonesia are asymmetrical and are implemented by state and non-state actors in various forms of direct and indirect threats (indirect or by proxy). Territorial boundaries that have not been ratified are even still being disputed so that they have an impact on the boundaries of the Exclusive Economic Zone that have not been determined, and not all of the territorial sea boundaries and continental shelf boundaries have been agreed with neighboring countries. Now physical threats have turned into threats that are not physical, but in fact these threats attack the security of citizens so that the term human security appears. Threats that attack human security to achieve freedom are carried out by destroying the citizens of a country through terrorism, drugs, illegal activities which in the end grouped into transnational crimes.

Indonesia as a strategic country whose geographical and geostrategic location is full of potential threats in the future can threaten Indonesia's freedom in carrying out maritime axis policies so that maritime axis policies are vulnerable to policy failure. Therefore, in order to improve national security and foster mutual trust, Indonesia needs regional and global cooperation to make the maritime axis policy a success. This regional and global cooperation is carried out as an effort to avoid the occurrence of an arms race (gun race) because each country seeks to balance its military strength (balance of power) because confidence has not yet grown.

3.3 Indonesia's Strategy in Realizing the Global Maritime Axis

One of the government programs in collaboration with the Ministry of Transportation is to encourage the sea highway program to continue to run by increasing capacity and services. This is because the sea highway will play a major role in connecting the archipelago's connectivity through water areas. We know that our country has long been known for its maritime power. We should maximize the existing potential with new breakthroughs to make Indonesia a strong, dignified and sovereign maritime country. The development of the sea highway is also an effort to realize the sea area as the centrality of policy, which is expected to be able to realize maritime security stability and national interests so that it has an impact on economic development and welfare. With this strategy, President Joko Widodo emphasized several things, including:

1. Local economic development is supported by the realization of infrastructure in advancing Indonesia's maritime economy. One of the development plans to support the maritime economic axis is the construction of the sea highway. We know that our island consists of $\pm 17,504$ islands, considering that it would take a long time to integrate these many islands into the ongoing economic activities. The sea toll will later be an effort to support effective sea connectivity, where it is hoped that in the future ships sailing in Indonesian waters will regularly and on a scheduled basis sail from the west to the east of Indonesia. The sea toll road will later serve as a liaison between islands and help access trade and industrialization in improving the welfare of the people and the country's economy. The concept of the sea toll road is also implemented as an improvement in the performance of sea transportation by improving domestic and international shipping networks, reducing dwelling time as an obstacle to the performance of national ports, as well as increasing the role of sea transportation. With subsidies and the construction of the sea highway, it is hoped that it can develop the economy, defense and territorial integrity of Indonesian waters.
2. President Joko Widodo wants to emphasize that the identity of the Indonesian nation is as a maritime country. This idea was later developed into a maritime security doctrine, with the emphasis that Indonesia must be sovereign because our archipelago is connected by the sea, besides that we must also strictly punish violations against foreign ships entering Indonesian waters without permission. If we get a foreign ship that enters Indonesian waters illegally, we must be firm to sink the ship, this is one of our forms of defense so that other countries do not carelessly enter our waters. The maritime area is the main vein of interaction of global interests, thus making maritime security a crucial issue for many countries in the world, not only seen from economic interests but also defense interests. Maritime stability is an important thing to do in order to maintain the interests and economic growth, as well as a

source of security. Geographical conditions in the form of islands and directly adjacent to a number of countries result in many threats that must be faced by Indonesia.

IV. CONCLUSION

Indonesia as the largest archipelagic country with a strategic geographical condition, is rich in natural resources, but all of them still cannot be utilized optimally for the prosperity of the nation. For this reason, the Joko Widodo government is trying to restore our country as a maritime country, one of which is through the Global Maritime Axis. In realizing this, of course, it is necessary to have support from the national defense system considering that our country is directly adjacent to several neighboring countries. Increasing maritime security is very important in maintaining the national jurisdiction area considering that Indonesia's seas are very wide. In addition, the potential threats that are now emerging are increasingly diverse, crimes can be carried out by sea. The most frequent occurrences are drug smuggling, illegal activities, and terrorism that occur in some of the borders of Indonesia's outermost sea areas. Strengthening defense needs to be pursued in view of maintaining national security and stability. Strategies such as the construction of the sea highway carried out by the government are expected to be a new breakthrough in protecting the marine areas of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI). By way of reaffirming our nation's identity as a maritime nation, of course this will make our people more alert and together help the government to maintain national defense because our country is a maritime country which of course needs support and integrity from all relevant parties to realize our goals. the aspirations of this nation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Nainggolan, P. P. Kebijakan Poros Maritim Dunia Joko Widodo dan Implikasi Internasionalnya. *Jurnal Politika*. 2015. Vol. 6, No. 2
- [2] Hidayat, S., & Ridwan. Kebijakan Poros Maritim dan Keamanan Nasional Indonesia: Tantangan dan Harapan. *Jurnal Pertahanan & Bela Negara*. 2017. Vol. 7, No. 3
- [3] Syarifudin, K. F., R., Deni Dadang, A., Nurcahyani, E., & Prakso, L. Y. Indonesia Poros Maritim Dunia: Mengembangkan Keamanan Nasional Melalui Perspektif Kerjasama Pertahanan di Kawasan. *Jurnal Strategi Perang Semesta*. 2017. Vol. 7, No. 1.
- [4] Ampun, A. C. R. A., & Purba, A. O. Strategi Pertahanan Maritim Indonesia Sebagai Poros Maritim Dunia. *Jurnal Ilmu Pengetahuan Sosial*. 2021. Vol. 8, No. 3.
- [5] Irianto, B. S. Kebijakan Poros Maritim Dan Strategi Ekonomi Serta Keamanan Laut. *Jurnal Justiciabelen*. 2021. Vol. 4, No. 1
- [6] Marsetio. Dalam Mendukung Pembangunan Indonesia Sebagai Negara Maritim Yang Tangguh. Available: <http://fri2016.uny.ac.id/sites/fri2016.uny.ac.id/files/5A2.%20MAKALAH%20%20DR.%20MARSETIO.pdf>. Accessed: 03-August-2021
- [7] Ardiyanti, Dwi. 2018. Indonesia sebagai Poros Maritim Dunia: Tantangan dan Peluang Keamanan dan Ekonomi Era Jokowi. *Jurnal Resolusi*. Vol.1, No.2.
- [8] Kementerian Koordinator Bidang Kemaritiman Republik Indonesia. 2017. https://maritim.go.id/konten/unggah/2017/07/Kebijakan_Kelautan_Indonesia_-_Indo_vers.pdf, Accessed: 03-August-2021
- [9] Atika, R. 2020. Tol Laut Bakal Bawa Indonesia jadi Poros Maritim Dunia. <https://www.liputan6.com/bisnis/read/4362293/tol-laut-bakal-bawa-indonesia-jadi-poros-maritim-dunia>. Accessed: 03-August-2021
- [10] Direktorat Pelayaran Pesisir dan Pulau-pulau Kecil. 2020. Konektivitas Pulau-pulau Kecil dan Terluar Melalui Pembangunan Dermaga Apung. <https://kkp.go.id/djprl/p4k/artikel/23196-konektivitas-pulau-pulau-kecil-dan-terluar-melalui-pembangunan-dermaga-apung>. Accessed: 03-August-2021
- [11] Syahrin, M. N. A. 2018. Kebijakan Poros Maritim Jokowi dan Sinergitas Strategi Ekonomi dan Keamanan Laut Indonesia. *Indonesian Perspective*. Vol. 3, No. 1